

EFFECT OF WEAVE ARCHITECTURE AND STUFFER TO BINDER RATIO ON MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF 3D-WOVEN COMPOSITE CORE-BASED SANDWICH PANELS

Prabhjot Singh¹, Javed Sheikh² and B. K. Behera³

¹Department of Textile and Fibre Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi,
Hauz Khas, New Delhi, India – 110016
Email: prbjotsingh.k@gmail.com

² Department of Textile and Fibre Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi,
Hauz Khas, New Delhi, India – 110016
Email: jnsheikh@iitd.ac.in, web page: <https://textile.iitd.ac.in>

³ Department of Textile and Fibre Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi,
Hauz Khas, New Delhi, India – 110016
Email: behera@iitd.ac.in, web page: <https://textile.iitd.ac.in>

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ABSTRACT

Metal-faced sandwich panels with solid composite cores are increasingly used in structural applications due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent fatigue resistance, stiffness, and superior impact tolerance. These characteristics make them ideal for demanding environments in aerospace, automotive, and defence sectors. However, conventional sandwich structures are often limited by core materials that lack sufficient delamination resistance and fail to distribute loads efficiently under extreme conditions. This study investigates the mechanical enhancement of fibre metal laminate (FML) sandwich panels by incorporating 3D-woven fabric-reinforced composite cores. Three weave architectures—3D orthogonal, 3D angle-interlock, and 3D warp-interlock—were explored across three stuffer-to-binder yarn ratios: 1:2, 1:1, and 2:1. Flexural testing revealed that the 3D angle-interlock cores exhibited the highest load-bearing capacity due to their inclined binder yarns that engage more effectively under bending stress. In contrast, 3D orthogonal cores demonstrated superior flexural stiffness, attributed to the near-vertical alignment of binder yarns enhancing through-thickness shear resistance. Panels with higher stuffer-to-binder ratios (2:1) consistently achieved greater peak loads and deflections, indicating enhanced energy absorption due to the increased volume of in-plane stuffer yarns. Notably, the 1:2 stuffer-to-binder ratio with an orthogonal weave offered a balanced improvement in both metrics. These findings offer valuable insights for designing high-performance sandwich composites for critical applications in the aerospace and defence sectors.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metal-faced sandwich panels with solid composite cores are advanced lightweight structural materials that combine the durability and strength of metal facesheets with the tailored properties of a solid composite core [1,2]. Typically, the facesheets are made from metals such as aluminum or stainless

steel, which provide excellent flexural stiffness, damage tolerance and surface hardness. The core, on the other hand, is a homogeneous composite material—often a polymer matrix composite—that offers excellent fatigue resistance, shear strength, and energy absorption. These characteristics make these composites ideal for demanding structural applications in aerospace, automotive, and defence sectors.

A lot of literature has already been published showing excellent fatigue resistance [3–5] and impact damage tolerance [6–8] of metal-faced sandwich panels with 2D and UD cores. They exhibit exceptional fatigue resistance, as the fibre layers act to arrest and slow the growth of cracks that initiate in the metal layers, significantly extending the material's lifespan under cyclic loading. FMLs are also highly damage-tolerant, maintaining much of their structural integrity even after sustaining impact or localized damage [9]. However, the flexural performance of conventional sandwich structures can be limited by the properties of the core material, which may struggle to effectively mitigate delamination and distribute loads under extreme conditions [10–12]. Numerous studies have investigated the flexural performance of metal-faced solid core sandwich structures, particularly those with unidirectional (UD) and 2D FRP cores. Lawcock et al. [13] reported that the flexural behaviour of CARALL laminates is highly influenced by the bonding strength at the metal–composite interface, which affects interlaminar shear but not tensile strength. To enhance flexural performance, several researchers have focused on improving interfacial adhesion in FML sandwich composites [14–16]. However, in designs prioritizing flexural modulus, increasing layer thickness has been shown to reduce flexural modulus linearly, with minimal impact on flexural strength [17].

Recent advancements in 3D-woven composites have demonstrated their potential to enhance the mechanical performance of FMLs over traditional two-dimensional (2D) woven and unidirectional (UD) composites, particularly in demanding engineering applications. One of the primary benefits is their superior resistance to delamination, a common failure mode in 2D and UD composites where layers separate under flexural or impact loading. This is achieved by incorporating fibers in the through-thickness (z) direction, which greatly enhances the structural integrity and reduces the risk of layer separation. Offering improved resistance to delamination, higher energy absorption, and more efficient load transfer [18,19]

The 3D-woven preforms can also be further modified to tailor the mechanical performance of the metal-faced sandwich composite panels by varying the weave architecture and stuffer-to-binder ratio of the woven preforms. As these two parameters are critical while determining the mechanical performance of the 3D-woven composites. Varying these parameters can further help analyse the change in the impact and flexural performance of the 3D-woven core-based metal-faced sandwich composite panels.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The sandwich panels used in this study incorporate three different types of 3D-woven solid composite core preforms: 3D orthogonal, 3D angle interlock, and 3D-warp interlock. All 3D core preforms are 4-layer to maintain consistency. A total of 9 core fabric preforms were fabricated, varying weave architecture and three different stuffer to binder ratios (1:2, 1:1, 2:1). The facesheets used are made of aluminium (Al-6063) with a thickness of 0.5mm. All samples were designed with identical dimensions: a core height of 2 mm and facesheet thickness of 0.5 mm. PLEXUS MA311 adhesive was used to bond the aluminium facesheets and core. The construction parameters of the core preforms are listed in Table 1. All core fabrics were fabricated using 600 tex E-glass rovings on a customized 3D rigid rapier weaving loom. A pictorial representation of the 3D orthogonal, 3D angle interlock, and 3D-warp interlock preforms is shown in Figure 1. All composite cores were consolidated using the Vacuum-Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VARTM) process, employing Epoxy LY556 resin and Aradur HY951 hardener.

Table 1: Construction parameters of 3D Solid Structures for core

Weave	3D orthogonal	3D angle interlock	3D warp interlock
Stuffer linear density (tex)	600	600	600
Binder linear density (Denier)	300	300	300
Filler linear density (Denier)	600	600	600
Number of stuffer layers	4	4	4
Number of filler layers	5	5	5
Stuffer + binder ends per inch	1:2 - 22	1:2 - 22	1:2 - 22
	1:1 - 30	1:1 - 30	1:1 - 30
	2:1 - 36	2:1 - 36	2:1 - 36
Filler ends per inch	10	10	10

Figure 1: (a-c) Weave design of different structures; (d-f) 3D-woven orthogonal fabrics with different stuffer-to-binder ratios

2.2 Preparation of sandwich panels

The sandwich structures were assembled using a hand layup method (illustrated in Fig. 2). Prior to bonding, the aluminium surfaces were sandblasted and cleaned with ethanol to improve adhesive bonding by removing surface contaminants. A uniform pressure was applied during bonding by placing a metallic plate of known weight over the sandwich assembly to expel entrapped air and ensure even adhesive distribution. To maintain a consistent adhesive layer, jigs were used to control the bond-line thickness, particularly at the corners. After the bonding process, the sandwich panels were allowed to cure at room temperature as per the adhesive manufacturer's recommendation. Following curing, the bonded sandwich panels were cut into standard test specimens using a precision band saw cutting machine. All specimens were inspected for uniformity in geometry and absence of visible defects before further testing.

2.3 Three-point bending

The three-point bending (TPB) tests on sandwich panels are conducted according to the ASTM D7264 standard. A characteristic label was used for each specimen to facilitate the analysis. The TPB tests were carried out on sandwich beams with different core types and aluminium and composite sheets of equivalent thickness. The span-to-width ratio was kept at 16:1, and the width of the sandwich panels was kept at 20mm. The Zwick Roell Z250 UTM machine was used for the tests with a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min for all TPB tests.

The flexural strength and flexural stiffness of the sandwich composite panels were calculated using equations 1 and 2,

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3P.L}{2bd^2} \quad (1)$$

Where σ_f is the flexural strength (MPa), P is the maximum load prior to failure (N), L is the span length (mm), b and d are the sandwich width (mm) and thickness (mm), respectively.

$$D = \frac{l^2 \cdot a \cdot \Delta P}{16f_1} \quad (2)$$

Where, D is the flexural stiffness (N.mm²), l is the span length (mm), a is overhanging arm length (mm), $\Delta P/f_1$ = slope of linear load-deformation curve (N/mm).

Figure 2: Sandwich preparation by Hand-layup process and final prepared 3D woven composite core sandwich panels

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Flexural Performance of Sandwich Composites

Figure 3 (a) and (b) illustrate the flexural strength and flexural stiffness, respectively, of aluminium-faced sandwich composites reinforced with 3D orthogonal, 3D angle-interlock, and 3D warp-interlock FRP cores. Each core configuration was studied at three different stuffer-to-binder yarn ratios: 1:2, 1:1, and 2:1.

From Fig. 3(a), it is evident that the 3D angle-interlock core sandwich panels consistently exhibited the highest flexural strength across all three stuffer-to-binder ratios. This was followed by the 3D orthogonal and then the 3D warp-interlock structures. The superior performance of the angle-interlock

architecture can be attributed to the orientation of its binder yarns, which are inclined rather than aligned purely in the thickness (Z) direction. This inclined arrangement enhances load transfer along the loading axis, thereby improving the panel's capacity to resist bending loads. Notably, the flexural strength increases with higher stuffer-to-binder ratios (from 1:2 to 2:1) in all three architectures, likely due to the increased volume of load-bearing stuffer yarns enhancing in-plane strength.

In contrast, the trend in flexural stiffness, as shown in Fig. 3(b), presents a different behaviour. The 3D orthogonal core sandwich panels demonstrated the highest flexural stiffness, especially prominent at the 1:2 stuffer-to-binder ratio. The orthogonal architecture benefits from binder yarns aligned nearly in the Z-direction, which enhances through-thickness stiffness and improves resistance to deformation under bending. The near-orthogonal arrangement of the binder, stuffer, and filler yarns contributes to a more integrated and rigid structure, improving shear stress transfer across the laminate. This results in a more uniform stress distribution during bending.

Interestingly, the flexural stiffness of the angle-interlock and orthogonal cores are nearly comparable at the 1:1 and 2:1 ratio, indicating that at equal or higher stuffer to binder ratios, angled binders can achieve stiffness close to that of orthogonal binders as the collective binder effect reduces per unit area. However, for the 1:2 ratio, the 3D orthogonal cores outperform the other two, while the warp-interlock configuration consistently shows the lowest flexural strength and stiffness in both graphs. This can be linked to the limited number of through-thickness binders in the warp-interlock design, which reduces the panel's resistance to both bending and shear deformation.

Figure 3: (a) Flexural strength; (b) flexural stiffness of sandwich panels with different core weave architecture and stuffer-to-binder ratio.

Figure 4 presents the load–displacement responses of sandwich panels with 3D orthogonal (OR), 3D angle-interlock (AI), and 3D warp-interlock (WI) composite cores under three different stuffer-to-binder ratios (1:2, 1:1, and 2:1). Specifically, Figure 2(a) compares the load–displacement curves of the three core architectures at a fixed 1:2 ratio, while Figures 4(b), 4(c), and 4(d) illustrate the effect of stuffer-to-binder ratio on the flexural behaviour of OR, AI, and WI cores, respectively.

From Figure 4(a), it is evident that the angle-interlock (AI) core exhibited the highest peak load, followed by the orthogonal (OR) and warp-interlock (WI) cores. The superior flexural load capacity of the AI core can be attributed to its angled binder yarns, which are better aligned with the direction of applied bending loads, allowing for enhanced load transfer and energy absorption. In contrast, the WI core, which contains fewer effective through-thickness reinforcements, shows the lowest peak load and early softening in the curve, indicating a reduced ability to resist delamination and through-thickness shear.

Figures 4(b–d) further reveal that increasing the stuffer-to-binder ratio consistently enhances the flexural load capacity across all core types. This trend is most evident in the AI and OR cores, where the 2:1 ratio configurations reach the highest peak loads. The improvement in performance at higher stuffer-to-binder ratios is due to the greater number of in-plane stuffer yarns per unit area, which directly contribute to carrying bending stresses. These yarns offer enhanced resistance to tensile and compressive forces developed on the tension and compression sides of the core during flexure.

Interestingly, the difference between the 1:2 and 1:1 configurations is minimal in terms of peak load, suggesting that the in-plane reinforcement (stuffers) is similar in both cases. However, a closer look at the slope of the initial linear region reveals that flexural stiffness is higher in the 1:2 ratio panels, especially for the OR cores (Fig. 2b). This increased stiffness can be attributed to the greater number of binder yarns in the through-thickness (Z) direction, which improve shear resistance and contribute to structural rigidity. On the other hand, the 2:1 configuration, despite showing the highest load-bearing capacity, exhibits slightly lower stiffness, particularly in WI cores (Fig. 4d), likely due to the reduced binder content, which weakens through-thickness integrity.

Figure 4: Load–displacement curves of sandwich panels with 3D OR, AI, and WI cores. (a) Comparison at 1:2 ratio; (b–d) effect of stuffer-to-binder ratios on OR, AI, and WI cores, respectively.

Figure 5 shows the post-flexural failure images of the sandwich panels reinforced with 3D angle-interlock, 3D orthogonal, and 3D warp-interlock composite cores, each tested at three different stuffer-to-binder ratios (1:2, 1:1, and 2:1). A consistent observation across all samples is the absence of

debonding or delamination between the core and the aluminum facesheets, indicating effective adhesive bonding and good interfacial integrity.

The dominant failure mode observed is a combination of core shear/yield, followed by bottom facesheet yielding under tension. During bending, the compressive stresses on the top face are absorbed without fracture, while the core initially undergoes localized deformation. As the loading progresses, the tension side of the panel (bottom facesheet) yields, ultimately leading to final failure. Samples with higher stuffer-to-binder ratios (2:1) exhibit larger deformation before failure, as evident from their more pronounced bending in Figure 5. This is because a higher ratio indicates greater in-plane stuffer yarn content, which enhances the core's ability to resist bending loads, delays the onset of failure, and allows more energy absorption. In contrast, the 1:2 specimens exhibit relatively smaller deformation, correlating with earlier onset of failure and reduced energy absorption due to fewer stuffer yarns available to share the in-plane tensile and compressive stresses.

These visual observations are in agreement with the flexural load-displacement curves presented earlier (Figure 4), where panels with a 2:1 ratio showed the highest load-bearing capacity and deflection before failure. While the external damage is visible, the internal core damage mechanisms, such as microcracking, yarn pull-out, or delamination within the core layers, remain areas of ongoing investigation and will be further studied using micro-computed tomography (μ CT) analysis for comprehensive damage assessment.

Figure 5: Fractured sandwich samples of different weave architecture (3D orthogonal, angle interlock, and warp interlock) and stuffer-to-binder ratio (1:2, 1:1, 2:1)

9 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the flexural behaviour of aluminium-faced sandwich composite panels reinforced with three different 3D woven core architectures—orthogonal, angle-interlock, and warp-interlock—at varying stuffer-to-binder ratios (1:2, 1:1, and 2:1). The results demonstrated that both core architecture and stuffer-to-binder ratio significantly influence the flexural strength, stiffness, and failure mechanisms of the sandwich panels.

Among the three architectures, the 3D angle-interlock core exhibited the highest flexural strength, attributed to its inclined binder yarns that effectively engage under bending loads. The 3D orthogonal core showed superior flexural stiffness, especially at lower stuffer-to-binder ratios, due to its vertically aligned Z-binders, which enhance through-thickness shear resistance. The 3D warp-interlock cores consistently exhibited lower mechanical performance, likely due to fewer effective through-thickness reinforcements.

An increase in the stuffer-to-binder ratio led to improved flexural load capacity across all core types, confirming that higher stuffer content enhances in-plane load distribution. However, this came at the expense of slightly reduced stiffness due to a corresponding decrease in binder yarns. Post-fracture analysis revealed that all panels failed through a combination of core shear/yielding and bottom facesheet tension failure, without any evidence of core–face debonding, indicating robust interfacial adhesion. The deformation profiles and fracture characteristics observed in flexural testing were consistent with the load-displacement behaviour, validating the role of textile architecture and yarn orientation in tailoring sandwich panel performance

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